

ADVANTAGES OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL WORK METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: This article provides information about what an interactive method is, its types, and also provides opinions on the use of interactive methods in education lessons, and relevant conclusions are drawn. The use of interactive methods in education lessons, especially in primary education, further increases the quality and effectiveness of education.

Keywords: Interactive methods, Educational science, Intelekart method, Cluster, Innovation, Incomplete pictures, circle method, Venn diagram

Introduction It is no exaggeration to say that the current era is increasingly full of changes and innovations, because the changes of today's era, every innovation and update in them, force people to live in harmony with this era. People are not only actively adapting to changes in all areas of the world, but also trying to live with these changes. Today, in an era where every process is rapidly developing, let's take every industry, and changes are inevitably affecting it. If we pay attention to every aspect, be it business, social sphere, even people's living environment, their style of dressing and various other areas are also attracting attention. People are creating innovations for themselves every day and implementing them in life. Living in a period of development, all countries in the world continue to develop in a competitive environment. In every field, they are moving forward with great strides to surpass each other and create innovations. At the same time, they are also conducting processes of exchange of experience with each other. Of course, these changes are taking place in almost all fields in the world, and great changes and opportunities are also being created in the field of education. Great opportunities and changes are being implemented throughout the world within the framework of the educational process, and at the same time, work is being carried out in our country to further reform, develop and further improve the education and upbringing system.

Our Honorable President has also signed many decrees and resolutions to further reform and develop the education and upbringing system. Today, great changes are being made in our country to bring the education and upbringing system to a higher level, covering not only school, higher education and all forms of further education. Various changes are being implemented and continue to be made to provide high-quality education to students. Serious attention is being paid to every aspect of the education sector, including the conditions and

opportunities, the level of knowledge of teachers, the scope and quality of subjects taught in the process of educating students, and we can say that everything is in the spotlight.

The dictionary meaning of the term "interactive" is "interactive" (eng. "interact"; "inter" - mutual, together, "act" - to act, to do work) means "to act together, together". Interactive methods are methods that establish cooperation between the learner and the teacher in the educational process, increase activity, effectively master knowledge by learners, and develop personal qualities in them. According to the studies of American psychologists R. Karnikau and F. McElrow, the natural physiological and psychological capabilities of a person allow them to retain acquired knowledge in certain forms to varying degrees. That is, a person:

- When reading the source himself 10%
- When hearing the information 20%
- When seeing an event, phenomenon or process that has occurred 30%
- When seeing an event, phenomenon or process that has occurred and hearing information about them 50%
- When transmitting information (information) himself (speaking, demonstrating knowledge) 80%
- When applying the acquired knowledge (information, information) to his activities, he has the ability to remember 90% of the information.[2]

Currently, the most popular interactive teaching methods are: Interactive methods. **“Case study” (or “Learning cases”), “Blister survey”, “Modeling”, “Creative work”, “Problem-based learning” and others. Interactive teaching strategies. “Brainstorming”, “Boomerang”, “Gallery”, “Zigzag”, “Step-by-step”, “Ice cream”, “Rotation”, “Rounded snow” and others.** The separation of interactive teaching strategies from the composition of interactive teaching methods is based on the fact that the approach to organizing group work is in a certain sense comparable to the strategic approach. In fact, these strategies also belong to interactive teaching methods to a greater extent, and there are no other differences between them. Interactive graphic organizers: **“Fishbone”, “BBB”, “Conceptual chart”, “Venn diagram”, “T-chart”, “Insert”, “Cluster”, “Why?”, “How?”**, etc. The distinction between interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that in such activities the main ideas are expressed in writing in various graphic forms...

In fact, working with graphic organizers also belongs to interactive teaching methods, and there are no other differences between them.[3] Nowadays, interest and attention to increasing the effectiveness of education using

interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process is growing day by day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students find the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and analyze it, and draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition of knowledge and education of the individual and the team, and at the same time performs the role of management and guidance. In such an educational process, the student becomes the main figure.

"Round table" method:

A sheet of paper with a task written on it is passed around in a circle. After each student writes down his answer option, he passes the sheet to another student. Then there is a discussion: incorrect answers are crossed out, and the student's knowledge is assessed based on the number of correct answers. This method can be used not only in written form, but also orally. Examples of tasks that can be given: - what are the components of education?; - what is the current demand for intellectual education?; - what are the tasks of moral education?; - what is the essence of ecological education?; - explain the important tasks of labor and economic education; - state the tasks of aesthetic education; - the importance of physical education today; - what are the important features of legal education? It should be remembered that a well-posed question is a question that contains half of the answer. The "pen in the middle of the table" method. The whole group is given a task (for example, to list the main factors affecting the development and formation of the student's personality, one by one). Each student writes one answer option on a piece of paper, gives it to his neighbor, and puts his pen in the middle of the table.

Example of an assignment: The teacher's assignment to the group is to explain the main factors affecting the development and formation of a person with real-life examples. Within the allotted 10-15 minutes, the group should give as many answer options as possible. The assignment, written on a sheet of paper, is passed from one student to another. The student writes the answer, passes the paper to the next student, and puts his pen on the table facing him. The student who does not know the answer passes the paper to the next student, but keeps his pen in his hand. Another condition of this methodology: it is impossible to give the same option twice, in other words, repetitions are not allowed here. The assignment is completed. The teacher has the paper with the answer options. He lists those options. As the options are listed, one of them is discussed: How do you explain the innate abilities of a person? What do you

understand by the social environment surrounding the child? Etc. The “pen in the middle of the table” method has several advantages. In particular, the teacher sees who is ready for the lesson and who is not:

Today, it is precisely for primary school students that knowledge is provided in various subjects, and the interactive methods mentioned above are now also being used in various subjects for primary school students. Interactive methods can be used not only in the field of exact sciences, but also in other additional subjects, and lessons can be conducted in a more interesting and diverse way. Currently, it is precisely for students that a single general subject, Education, which combines several subjects, such as **"Etiquette"**, **"Sense of Homeland"**, **"The Idea of National Independence and the Foundations of Spirituality"**, and **"History of World Religions"**, has been introduced, and students are being provided with knowledge in this subject. Education is taught not only in primary schools, but also to high school students. The introduction of the subject of Education is also an indication that students are not only given knowledge, but also moral knowledge in schools. Among other subjects, by conducting lesson processes using interactive methods from the perspective of education, among other subjects, this subject will be taught in a more creative way, the lesson process will not be limited to the textbook, but will also help to reinforce the topic covered using the method, and prevent students from getting bored. In addition, through various interactive methods, we will have the opportunity to work together individually, in pairs, and in teams through the subject of education. Various interactive methods can be used in the process of teaching the subjects of education, and through these, we will be able to better complement the subject we are teaching, and students will have the opportunity to convey knowledge and delve deeper into the subject.

Using the topics given in the subject of education, we will consider as examples how several interactive methods can be applied to the topics of this subject. **"Cluster" GO ("Cluster" – bud, bundle, bundle)** is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used with students in individual and group classes. Clusters create the opportunity to generalize the ideas put forward, to find connections between them [4,76-b] The cluster method can be used in various disciplines, including education. Specifically, when writing a concept in the subject of education, using the cluster method, students can fill it with thoughts about the given concept by writing the appropriate words in the circles around it. Today, education is provided in various subjects specifically for primary school students, and the interactive methods mentioned above are currently being used

in various subjects for primary school students. In the process of teaching the subjects of education, various interactive methods can be used, and through them we will be able to further enrich the topic we are studying, and students will have the opportunity to better convey knowledge and delve deeper into the subject. Using the topics given in education, we will consider as examples how several interactive methods can be applied to the topics of this subject. "Cluster" GO ("Cluster" - a bud, a bundle, a bundle) is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used with students in individual and group classes. Clusters create the opportunity to generalize the ideas put forward and find connections between them [4,76-b] The cluster method can be used in various disciplines, including education. Specifically, when writing a concept about education, using the cluster method, learners can fill it with thoughts about the given concept by writing appropriate words in the circles around it.

Conclusion, we can say that today, it is necessary to teach each lesson effectively and in a high-quality manner. Today's students are growing up in a modern way in every respect, and therefore they strive to acquire knowledge at a similar level. Therefore, each student should be given knowledge in a specific way, that is, they should be given thorough knowledge from the point of view of each subject, using various interactive methods, and using each topic covered in the lesson in a way that strengthens it. This not only increases the effectiveness of the lesson, but also increases the level of opportunities for students. Because today's demand is to provide each student with a high level of knowledge, to develop them into highly competent individuals who are modern and formed in a modern way.

References:

1. Sanakulov Kh.R., Khodiyeva D.P. Satbayeva "Labor and its teaching methodology". Textbook. T.: TDPU. 2015.
2. Sh. Mirziyoyev We will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan together. Tashkent – "Uzbekistan" – 2016.56B.
3. M. Tilavova "Technology and its teaching methodology" textbook M. Bukhara: OOO" Sadridin Salim Bukhariy "Durdona, 2021-312b.
4. Sh. N. KURBONOVA: Application of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS. Special issue, 2020 102 pages
5. Use of interactive methods in the educational process. Bozorova Rozigul/Safiyeva Shohista Shuhrat kizi article.
6. Special Subject Teaching Methodology. O.U.Avlayev, S.R.Mirzayeva, Sh.R.Samarova. Tashkent-2022, p. 73. 3. Special Subject Teaching Methodology. O.U.Avlayev, S.R.Mirzayeva, Sh.R.Samarova. Tashkent-2022, p. 83.

7. Creative Pedagogy. B.E.Karimova. Tashkent "Innovation-Intellect", 2022, p. 76.

8. <https://www.yoshlarovozi.uz/oz/news/beshinchisi-ortiqcha>

